

Pixel Labeler: A Pixel-wise Annotation Tool for Active Learning Music Recognition

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Abstract. Pixel-wise image annotation is a critical but demanding task, particularly in domains where precise labeling is essential for training supervised models. In this work, we present a novel annotation tool designed to assist with Optical Music Recognition (OMR) tasks and to support human-in-the-loop workflows within Active Learning (AL) cycles. The tool focuses on maximizing annotation efficiency and user experience by combining a lightweight interface, usability-driven design, and support for fine-grained, per-pixel semantic labeling. Preliminary results suggest that the proposed interface can reduce the cognitive and operational burden on annotators, offering a viable solution for tasks requiring dense annotations. Feedback from domain users, as well as informal metrics such as annotation time and perceived usability, support the relevance of the design. Overall, this work contributes a flexible and user-centered annotation interface that lays the groundwork for more efficient and effective integration of human input in OMR and AL-based image segmentation workflows.

Keywords: Optical Music Recognition (OMR) · Active Learning · Dataset annotation.

1 Introduction

Optical Music Recognition (OMR) plays a fundamental role in preserving and providing digital access to historical musical heritage [5]. By converting fragile physical scores—both printed and handwritten—into machine-readable formats, OMR enables searchable digital libraries and facilitates large-scale musicological research. However, early music documents often suffer from severe visual degradations, such as irregular layouts, faded ink, yellowed paper, and damaged or distorted symbols, resulting from aging and manual or printing inconsistencies [12]. These conditions pose significant challenges for automatic recognition, especially for machine learning methods that depend on large volumes of high-quality labeled data.

Active Learning (AL) emerges as a promising strategy. AL enables models to be trained using a reduced set of labeled instances, selecting the most informative samples to be labeled by a human expert. This is particularly beneficial in the context of OMR, where full annotation of high-resolution images of complex scores is time-consuming and expensive, as AL enables human annotators to focus on the most challenging areas of a score. Moreover, because recognition errors are common in degraded historical sources, interactive systems involving a human-in-the-loop become highly valuable. These systems allow for incremental improvement through expert feedback, contrasting with traditional OMR pipelines that are static and non-adaptive [4].

Yet, effective integration of AL into OMR workflows demands specialized annotation tools. Pixel-level annotation is particularly useful for complex tasks such as layout analysis or semantic segmentation, where bounding boxes may fall short—for instance, when symbols overlap or have irregular shapes that cannot be precisely enclosed. Music scores, due to their heterogeneity, dense notation, and close symbol proximity, require precise annotation capabilities tailored to domain-specific challenges. The lack of dedicated tools for fine-grained annotation of music documents remains a bottleneck in generating training data necessary to advance OMR technologies.

To address this gap, we present a novel annotation tool designed for pixel-level labeling of music documents, with a particular focus on tasks in OMR and AL pipelines. The tool is built to be both accessible to domain experts such as musicologists—who may not have technical expertise—and precise enough to support high-quality annotation. Our approach aims to bridge the gap between machine learning systems and expert annotators, enabling efficient dataset creation and continuous model refinement with minimal manual effort.

2 State of the Art

AL has emerged as an effective strategy for reducing annotation costs by directing human effort toward the most informative and uncertain samples. This approach has proven valuable across diverse domains where dense annotations are costly. In historical document processing, Narag et al. [8] demonstrated how selective expert interventions, guided by model uncertainty, can effectively restore severely degraded architectural drawings with minimal manual input. Similarly, Budd et al. [3] emphasized the role of AL in medical image analysis, where careful sample selection significantly lowers labeling effort while maintaining clinical accuracy. In the context of semantic segmentation, Kasarla et al. [7] introduced a region-based AL framework that prioritizes superpixels for annotation, achieving high performance with only a fraction of the pixel labels. Together, these studies underscore AL’s potential to optimize annotation efficiency in visual.

Nonetheless, effectively incorporating AL into OMR workflows requires more than selective sampling. It also demands annotation tools that support pixel-level precision and enable seamless integration into iterative, human-in-the-loop processes. This is particularly critical in the context of early music documents,

where dense layouts, irregular symbol shapes, and visual degradation challenge conventional annotation methods.

Existing tools vary greatly in their design, goals, and capabilities. Some are general-purpose image editors repurposed for annotation; others are built for computer vision tasks like object detection or semantic segmentation. A smaller subset focuses on model-assisted correction [9, 10, 1], which aligns closely with AL workflows. Each type offers distinct advantages and limitations depending on the level of granularity required and the nature of the target documents.

To clarify these differences, Table 1 summarizes the representative tools across these categories, highlighting their features and limitations. Despite the variety of tools, none of them fully meets the requirements for dense, pixel-level annotation of music documents. General-purpose editors offer precision but lack structured workflows and class management. Region-based platforms provide semantic labeling but fall short in granularity and control. Pixel-wise tools, while more precise, often do not support multilayer annotations or iterative correction workflows. Finally, correction-focused systems are tightly coupled to specific pipelines and lack flexibility for arbitrary pixel editing.

Table 1: Comparison of annotation tools based on functionality, granularity, and suitability for music document labeling.

Type \ Tool	Main features	Limitations
General-purpose image editing		
Photoshop, GIMP, Pixelmator	Precise pixel editing, layer support	No class tracking; lacks data export and structured annotation; not suitable for large-scale workflows
Picozu	Web-based, layer support, basic drawing tools	Low performance on large files; no annotation features or export formats
Object/region-based annotation		
LabelImg, makesense.ai, LabelMe	Open-source; supports bounding boxes and polygons; standard export formats (COCO, VOC, YOLO)	No pixel-level support; unsuitable for fine-grained segmentation
CVAT	Web-based, collaborative, supports tracking, automation plugins	Region-focused; lacks tools for pixel correction or dense symbol handling
VIA (VGG Image Annotator)	Lightweight browser tool for polygons, points, rectangles; export to JSON/CSV	No advanced editing or segmentation refinement
Pixel-wise annotation tools		
Supervisely	Pixel-level tools (brush, fill, eraser); supports object labeling	No multilayer editing; not tailored for iterative correction
Correction-focused tools		
MuRET [9]	Complete OMR pipeline; symbol-level annotation; integrated AL loop	No free-form pixel tools (brush/fill); focused on region/symbol annotations
Pixel.js [10]	Web-based; pixel-level correction via layer interface; designed for score segmentation	Limited multilabel control; post-segmentation correction only
WebGT [1]	Web tool for historical layout annotation; supports rectangles; collaborative mode	No fine-grained pixel editing or multilabel overlay support

3 Pixel Labeler

We developed a custom pixel-level annotation tool (Pixel Labeler) in Python, designed to address the challenges of precisely labeling historical music scores, while remaining flexible enough for other types of music notation or imagery. These documents often suffer from visual degradation, such as paper yellowing, ink fading, stains, and other noise artifacts that hinder automated segmentation methods. Therefore, manual pixel-level annotation remains crucial in this context, and the proposed tool has been designed to effectively meet these specific requirements. Pixel Labeler is released as open-source software¹, encouraging transparency, reproducibility, and community-driven improvement.

The first step when using the tool is to configure a list of independent layers that will represent all the types of information to be annotated—such as staff lines, text, musical notes, or even decorative ornaments. This setup is done by editing a simple configuration text file that specifies the name and display color of each layer. The file is reusable across images, so it only needs to be defined once. The annotation process is thus organized into a set of customizable layers, enabling a clear separation of different semantic elements within the score. This design supports focused annotation and facilitates subsequent analysis.

Pixel Labeler provides three complementary annotation methods:

- **Freehand pen**, with adjustable brush size, for direct drawing.
- **Magic wand selector**, which segments connected regions based on a user-adjustable threshold. The selected region is displayed in real time, and the threshold can be dynamically increased or decreased using keyboard shortcuts. The tool also includes built-in expansion and reduction operations to refine the selection. By default, it applies an automatic smoothing step that combines an initial expansion followed by a contraction, effectively filling small gaps often caused by stains, faded ink, or degraded paper texture.
- **Bucket fill**, for rapid labeling of uniform areas (with threshold control).

One key feature of Pixel Labeler is its default behavior of protecting annotations across layers. Editing operations avoid modifying pixels already labeled in other layers, reducing the risk of accidental overwrites. This helps maintain consistency in multi-layer annotation workflows, while still allowing users to disable the safeguard when overwriting is needed.

The interface is optimized for annotator productivity, including intuitive keyboard shortcuts for fast switching between tools and layers, undo actions, zoom/pan controls, and adjusting tool size or threshold values. The live visual feedback and multi-layer awareness enhance the user experience when working with complex manuscripts. Figure 1 shows an example of the annotation process using the tool on a music score image. It illustrates the high pixel-level precision of the interface and its multi-layer annotation capabilities. To further assist annotators, it includes a progress bar that displays the percentage of the image that has been annotated. Additionally, users can enable a visualization mode

¹ <https://github.com/cperez/pixel-level-annotator>

that highlights all unannotated pixels, making it easy to identify and complete any missing regions without resorting to manual pixel-spotting.

Fig. 1: User interface of the annotation tool, showing multi-layer control, tool selection, and real-time visual feedback.

Each annotation session results in a set of binary images, one per layer, where pixels belonging to the corresponding semantic class are set to one and the rest to zero. These images serve as segmentation masks and can be directly used for training or evaluating machine learning models (see Figure 2). Additionally, a metadata file is generated, containing information such as the time spent annotating each layer. This temporal information enables further research on annotator behavior and task complexity. For example, it can be used to identify particularly challenging layers, analyze the efficiency of different tools or annotation strategies, or model the annotation cost for AL prioritization.

3.1 Interoperability and Integration

The annotation tool is designed for interoperability and integrates easily into broader annotation workflows through a lightweight HTTP-based communication mechanism, exchanging data with other applications using standard web requests. It launches a local service that accepts requests containing: (1) the image to be annotated, (2) the definition of annotation layers, and (3) a callback URL to which the completed annotations are sent upon marking the image as

Fig. 2: Pixel-level annotation outputs. From left to right: original image and binary masks for background, staff lines, notes, and lyrics layers.

annotated. Although implemented in Python and run locally, this setup allows seamless integration with web-based annotation systems, enabling dynamic task dispatch and transparent coordination in collaborative or large-scale projects.

4 Evaluation

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed annotation tool, an evaluation was conducted with five expert human annotators ($\mathcal{H}_1 - \mathcal{H}_5$). Each participant labeled the same image set using both Pixel Labeler and GIMP. This dual annotation enabled direct comparison across three dimensions: annotation time, inter- and intra-annotator agreement, and usability.

GIMP was chosen as the baseline due to its overlap in pixel-level editing capabilities. Most annotation platforms focus on object- or region-based labeling and lack support for free-form pixel editing. GIMP, in contrast, offers essential tools like brush, eraser, layers, and zoom, allowing users to manually create or refine segmentation masks. While not an annotation tool per se, its flexibility and widespread use make it a practical benchmark. However, obtaining usable mask outputs for training or evaluation requires exporting each layer individually as an image, which adds an extra step compared to the direct export functionality of the proposed tool. As a free, open-source, and cross-platform application, it also provides a neutral baseline for evaluating usability and efficiency. To ensure consistency across tools, all annotators were given a common set of guidelines on how to approach the annotation task.

4.1 Dataset

The evaluation was conducted using three publicly available datasets containing historical music manuscripts, each annotated at the pixel level with four semantic layers: **staff**, **notes**, **text**, and **background**.

Rather than conducting large-scale training experiments, our focus is on evaluating the annotation process itself, as a step toward integrating the proposed tool into an AL loop in future work. To emulate realistic usage within such a loop, where fragment selection is guided by model-based or heuristic criteria, we

extracted 256×256 pixel patches from each dataset. A total of 15 patches (5 per dataset) were selected for annotation, resulting in 983,040 pixels labeled per annotator and tool. Full images are typically not used in this context because historical musical documents are large, heterogeneous, and often contain substantial regions that do not require annotation (e.g., margins or blank areas). Focusing on representative patches enables a more efficient and targeted evaluation, while better reflecting the iterative nature of AL, where only small but informative regions are selected for labeling at each step.

The datasets span a range of notational styles and historical contexts, offering a representative subset of the visual and semantic variability encountered in historical document annotation and serving as a suitable context for evaluating annotation workflows under controlled but realistic conditions:

- **EINSIEDELN**: 9 high-resolution scans of neumatic notation from the *Einsiedeln, Stiftsbibliothek, Codex 611(89)* (1314).²
- **SALZINNES**: 10 images from the *Salzannes Antiphonal* (CDM-Hsmu M2149.14), also in neumatic notation, accessible via the *Cantus Ultimus* platform.³
- **CAPITAN** [6]: 10 double-page images of mensural notation from the 17th–18th centuries, sourced from the *Cathedral of Our Lady of the Pillar*, Zaragoza, Spain.⁴

4.2 Annotation Time

Table 2 summarizes the average annotation time per layer and dataset, including standard deviation, for both tools. Overall, the results show that the proposed tool notably reduces annotation time, especially for complex layers such as **staff** and **notes**. On simpler layers like **background**, both tools yield comparable times. Therefore, these outcomes suggest that Pixel Labeler offers a more efficient and consistent annotation experience.

As shown in Table 3, Pixel Labeler achieved an average time saving of 2:19 (mm:ss) per image, reducing the mean annotation time from 10:31 to 8:12—a 22% improvement in efficiency across annotators. The largest gains were seen in the **staff** and **lyrics** layers, where the structured content benefits most from the tool’s tailored interaction mechanisms.

While some annotators experienced longer times for the simpler **background** layer, this was offset by notable savings in the more demanding layers. An in-depth analysis of total annotation times reveals that using Pixel Labeler reduced the overall annotation effort from 47,321 seconds (~13h 9min) to 36,872 seconds (~10h 15min).

4.3 Agreement

To evaluate annotation consistency, we measured both inter-annotator and intra-annotator agreement across all annotated layers, comparing results obtained

² <http://www.e-codices.unifr.ch/en/sbe/0611/>

³ <https://cantus.simssa.ca/manuscript/123723/>

⁴ RISM Code “E-Zac” available at <https://rism.info>.

Table 2: Average annotation time per patch (mm:ss±std) for each layer and total, across three datasets, annotated by each human annotator \mathcal{H}_n . The left columns report annotation times using GIMP, while the right columns use the proposed Pixel Labeler tool. Times correspond to the average of five annotated patches per dataset and layer. Bold values indicate the fastest annotation times per case.

Ann. Layer	GIMP				Pixel Labeler				
	CAPITAN	EINSIEDELN	SALZINNES	Avg.	CAPITAN	EINSIEDELN	SALZINNES	Avg.	
\mathcal{H}_1	Bg.	00:41 _{±00:15}	00:28 _{±00:13}	00:22 _{±00:04}	00:31 _{±00:10}	01:00 _{±00:50}	02:02 _{±01:18}	00:30 _{±00:23}	01:10 _{±00:47}
	Staff	03:50 _{±01:08}	02:20 _{±00:29}	03:08 _{±01:49}	03:06 _{±00:45}	02:23 _{±01:30}	03:02 _{±00:44}	02:15 _{±00:41}	02:33 _{±00:25}
	Notes	02:41 _{±00:36}	02:42 _{±01:10}	02:50 _{±00:57}	02:44 _{±00:05}	02:07 _{±01:16}	03:31 _{±02:06}	01:15 _{±00:54}	02:18 _{±01:09}
	Lyrics	02:48 _{±00:43}	04:03 _{±01:45}	03:16 _{±01:00}	03:22 _{±00:38}	01:33 _{±00:39}	02:09 _{±01:29}	01:00 _{±00:36}	01:34 _{±00:35}
	Total	10:00 _{±01:11}	09:32 _{±01:58}	09:36 _{±02:09}	09:43 _{±00:15}	07:04 _{±01:03}	10:44 _{±03:38}	05:00 _{±01:04}	07:36 _{±02:54}
\mathcal{H}_2	Bg.	00:37 _{±00:06}	00:39 _{±00:09}	00:41 _{±00:07}	00:39 _{±00:02}	00:16 _{±00:05}	00:18 _{±00:07}	00:21 _{±00:24}	00:19 _{±00:03}
	Staff	04:12 _{±00:51}	02:36 _{±01:25}	01:55 _{±00:41}	02:54 _{±01:10}	04:31 _{±02:17}	03:21 _{±02:28}	01:35 _{±00:59}	03:09 _{±01:29}
	Notes	02:56 _{±00:36}	03:58 _{±01:25}	02:50 _{±00:44}	03:15 _{±00:38}	01:59 _{±01:13}	01:31 _{±01:15}	01:40 _{±00:47}	01:43 _{±00:14}
	Lyrics	03:33 _{±00:38}	03:20 _{±01:29}	03:56 _{±01:18}	03:36 _{±00:18}	01:03 _{±00:36}	00:59 _{±00:40}	01:28 _{±00:51}	01:10 _{±00:15}
	Total	11:17 _{±01:05}	10:34 _{±02:26}	09:21 _{±02:22}	10:24 _{±00:59}	07:49 _{±02:52}	06:10 _{±03:27}	05:04 _{±01:28}	06:21 _{±02:23}
\mathcal{H}_3	Bg.	00:38 _{±00:06}	00:33 _{±00:06}	00:40 _{±00:08}	00:37 _{±00:04}	01:17 _{±00:41}	00:56 _{±00:27}	00:47 _{±00:25}	01:00 _{±00:15}
	Staff	03:56 _{±01:04}	03:03 _{±01:17}	02:09 _{±00:51}	03:03 _{±00:53}	03:41 _{±01:22}	01:37 _{±00:38}	00:47 _{±00:25}	02:02 _{±01:30}
	Notes	02:41 _{±00:23}	02:36 _{±01:00}	02:18 _{±00:26}	02:32 _{±00:12}	03:01 _{±00:36}	02:09 _{±00:33}	02:08 _{±00:49}	02:26 _{±00:30}
	Lyrics	02:31 _{±00:24}	02:51 _{±01:02}	03:07 _{±01:05}	02:50 _{±00:18}	02:09 _{±00:21}	00:23 _{±00:04}	01:47 _{±01:13}	01:26 _{±00:56}
	Total	09:47 _{±00:57}	09:03 _{±02:01}	08:15 _{±01:43}	09:01 _{±00:46}	10:07 _{±01:41}	05:05 _{±01:10}	05:29 _{±02:26}	06:54 _{±02:48}
\mathcal{H}_4	Bg.	00:53 _{±00:21}	00:31 _{±00:15}	00:36 _{±00:09}	00:40 _{±00:12}	02:26 _{±01:12}	01:50 _{±00:38}	00:53 _{±00:23}	01:43 _{±00:47}
	Staff	08:00 _{±02:26}	03:30 _{±00:29}	02:10 _{±00:27}	04:33 _{±03:03}	03:21 _{±00:55}	03:19 _{±01:54}	04:12 _{±02:37}	03:37 _{±00:30}
	Notes	04:05 _{±01:59}	03:12 _{±01:13}	03:26 _{±00:41}	03:34 _{±00:27}	01:47 _{±02:44}	01:57 _{±01:30}	03:58 _{±00:53}	02:34 _{±01:13}
	Lyrics	02:18 _{±00:23}	03:45 _{±00:33}	04:03 _{±00:52}	03:22 _{±00:56}	04:51 _{±00:28}	01:49 _{±01:29}	02:20 _{±01:31}	03:00 _{±01:37}
	Total	15:15 _{±04:37}	10:58 _{±01:33}	10:16 _{±00:28}	12:09 _{±02:42}	12:25 _{±03:38}	08:55 _{±04:40}	11:24 _{±03:21}	10:55 _{±01:48}
\mathcal{H}_5	Bg.	00:41 _{±00:17}	00:27 _{±00:06}	00:23 _{±00:05}	00:30 _{±00:09}	02:36 _{±01:32}	00:22 _{±00:15}	00:20 _{±00:27}	01:06 _{±01:18}
	Staff	06:48 _{±01:53}	02:58 _{±00:44}	03:32 _{±00:36}	04:26 _{±02:04}	05:27 _{±00:51}	02:11 _{±00:20}	00:48 _{±00:32}	02:49 _{±02:23}
	Notes	02:46 _{±00:08}	03:09 _{±01:14}	03:34 _{±00:29}	03:10 _{±00:24}	03:51 _{±00:45}	03:33 _{±00:55}	02:39 _{±00:37}	03:21 _{±00:37}
	Lyrics	03:10 _{±00:31}	03:35 _{±00:42}	02:48 _{±00:57}	03:11 _{±00:24}	02:16 _{±01:13}	01:32 _{±01:06}	02:03 _{±00:30}	01:57 _{±00:22}
	Total	13:25 _{±02:00}	10:09 _{±02:19}	10:17 _{±01:04}	11:17 _{±01:51}	14:10 _{±02:04}	07:38 _{±01:22}	05:51 _{±01:03}	09:13 _{±04:23}
Avg.	Bg.	00:42 _{±00:07}	00:31 _{±00:05}	00:32 _{±00:09}	00:35 _{±00:05}	01:31 _{±00:59}	01:06 _{±00:49}	00:34 _{±00:15}	01:04 _{±00:30}
	Staff	05:21 _{±01:55}	02:53 _{±00:27}	02:35 _{±00:43}	03:36 _{±00:49}	03:53 _{±01:10}	02:42 _{±00:46}	01:55 _{±01:25}	02:50 _{±00:36}
	Notes	03:02 _{±00:36}	03:07 _{±00:33}	03:00 _{±00:31}	03:03 _{±00:25}	02:33 _{±00:52}	02:32 _{±00:56}	02:20 _{±01:03}	02:28 _{±00:35}
	Lyrics	02:52 _{±00:30}	03:31 _{±00:27}	03:26 _{±00:32}	03:16 _{±00:17}	02:22 _{±01:28}	01:23 _{±00:42}	01:44 _{±00:31}	01:49 _{±00:43}
	Total	11:57 _{±01:54}	10:03 _{±01:21}	09:33 _{±01:17}	10:31 _{±01:23}	10:19 _{±00:59}	07:42 _{±00:49}	06:33 _{±00:45}	08:12 _{±00:47}

with Pixel Labeler and GIMP. Agreement was computed as the mean pixel-wise overlap percentage across the corresponding annotations.

As shown in Table 4, Pixel Labeler achieved slightly higher inter-annotator agreement (96.66%±2.28) than GIMP (95.67%±3.22), consistently outperforming it across all annotation layers. The largest improvement was observed in the **background** layer, with a 3.22 percentage point gain. Notable gains were also seen in the **notes** layer. In addition, Pixel Labeler exhibited lower standard deviations in most cases, indicating more consistent annotation behavior among users. These results suggest that the tool’s interaction mechanisms help reduce manual variability, increase detail refinement, and promote more uniform annotations.

Intra-annotator agreement, measured by comparing annotations made by the same user with GIMP and Pixel Labeler, averaged 96.81%±2.88 across all layers.

Table 3: Annotation time saved (mm:ss±std) when using Pixel Labeler, in comparison with GIMP, shown per annotator \mathcal{H}_n , for each annotation layer and in total. Values represent the average difference over 15 patches (5 per dataset: CAPITAN, EINSIEDELN, and SALZINNES). Positive values (in green) indicate time savings, while negative values (in red) indicate longer annotation times.

	Time saved per layer				Total saved
	Bg.	Staff	Notes	Lyrics	
\mathcal{H}_1	-00:40±00:47	+00:33±00:23	+00:26±00:31	+01:48±00:30	+02:07±01:42
\mathcal{H}_2	+00:20±00:01	-00:15±00:15	+01:32±00:49	+02:26±00:05	+04:03±00:31
\mathcal{H}_3	-00:23±00:16	+01:01±00:40	+00:06±00:08	+01:24±01:03	+02:08±01:51
\mathcal{H}_4	-01:03±00:40	+00:56±02:14	+01:00±00:53	+00:22±00:26	+01:15±00:51
\mathcal{H}_5	-00:36±01:04	+01:37±01:00	-00:11±00:22	+01:14±00:43	+02:04±01:51
Avg.	-00:36±00:24	+00:52±00:39	+00:39±00:05	+01:27±00:51	+02:19±00:41

Table 4: Inter-annotator and intra-annotator agreement (%) by annotation layer and tool. Values indicate mean agreement with standard deviation.

*Statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Layer	Inter-annotator agreement		
	Pixel Labeler	GIMP	Intra-Annotator
Background	94.18 ±3.45	90.96 ±8.75	94.24 ±2.83
Staff	97.84 ±1.09	97.80 ±0.88	97.67 ±1.53
Notes	*97.88 ±1.28	97.24 ±1.54	98.18 ±1.29
Lyrics	96.74 ±3.62	96.66 ±2.17	97.16 ±2.88
Average	96.66 ±2.98	95.67 ±5.27	96.81 ±2.88

This ~3% discrepancy, mostly due to differences in boundary precision, highlights the inherent variability in manual annotation. Notably, the inter-annotator agreement with Pixel Labeler approaches this level, underscoring its potential to promote consistent results across users.

To assess the significance of agreement differences, we performed a Wilcoxon test on agreement values. Although the average agreement was 0.99 percentage points higher with Pixel Labeler, the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.071$). This suggests a trend toward improved consistency, though more data is needed to confirm it.

Layer-wise comparisons showed that the most significant improvement occurred in the **notes** layer, where agreement with Pixel Labeler was higher by 0.64 percentage points ($p = 0.022$). The **background** layer also showed a mean gain of 3.21 points; however, this result was not statistically significant ($p = 0.454$) and therefore should be interpreted with caution. For the **staff** and **lyrics** layers, we did not find statistically significant evidence of differences. These findings suggest that Pixel Labeler may provide measurable benefits particularly in complex, high-density regions such as musical notes, where symbols are often small,

overlapping, or in close contact with staff lines—conditions that make manual segmentation more error-prone. In contrast, lyrics tend to be visually separated and less ambiguous, which may explain why no statistically reliable differences were detected in that layer. A visual example of agreement distributions across annotators per layer is shown in Figure 3, where most disagreement can be observed around the boundaries of the annotated regions.

Fig. 3: Agreement analysis among annotators for the patch shown in Figure 2a. Each subfigure displays a heatmap representing the level of agreement for a specific layer (**background**, **staff**, **notes**, and **lyrics**), where blue indicates full agreement among all annotators and red denotes disagreement.

Additionally, a detailed inspection of the annotated masks revealed that, when using GIMP, annotators occasionally left pixels unlabelled. On average, 6.1 pixels per patch remained unannotated, with some patches showing up to 65 missing labels (pixels). This type of omission was not observed when using the proposed tool, thanks to its utility for reviewing annotation completeness, highlighting an additional benefit in completeness and robustness.

Overall, the consistency observed both between and within annotators confirms that Pixel Labeler supports precise and reproducible pixel-level annotations across diverse content types.

4.4 Usability and User Experience Evaluation

To assess the usability of Pixel Labeler, we conducted the standardized *System Usability Scale (SUS)* questionnaire [2], which consists of 10 items rated on a five-point Likert scale and yields a usability score ranging from 0 to 100.

All annotators completed the SUS questionnaire immediately after the annotation session. The resulting scores ranged from 82.5 to 95.0, with a mean value of 91.0. Based on established benchmarks, these scores reflect excellent usability for Pixel Labeler, with consistently positive perceptions regarding clarity, ease of use, and interaction efficiency.

In addition to usability, user experience was assessed using the short version of the *User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ-S)* [11], which captures two core dimensions: Pragmatic Quality (e.g., clarity, task support) and Hedonic Quality

(e.g., aesthetics, enjoyment). Pixel Labeler received high ratings in both dimensions, with mean scores of 2.15 (Pragmatic) and 1.95 (Hedonic), and an overall average of 2.05 on a scale from -3 to $+3$.

Together, these findings demonstrate that Pixel Labeler not only achieves high usability, but also delivers a pleasant and engaging user experience.

In addition to standardized instruments, participants answered an open-ended questionnaire to provide qualitative feedback. The responses highlighted several positive aspects of the tool, such as its simplicity, intuitive keyboard shortcuts, and efficient region selection. All annotators reported feeling faster compared to other tools, attributing this to well-designed interaction design and easy shortcut availability. While most feedback was positive, some participants suggested improvements including enhanced threshold control, zoom precision, and the addition of alternative brush types.

5 Conclusions

This work introduces Pixel Labeler, a pixel-wise image annotation tool designed to integrate within Optical Music Recognition (OMR) and Active Learning (AL) cycles. This tool enables human oracles to efficiently interact with selected samples, aiming to maximize the value of each annotation while minimizing manual effort through a usability-driven and workflow-optimized interface.

This exploratory case study suggests that the tool is suitable for its intended purpose. Metrics such as annotation time, qualitative feedback, and ease of use point toward potential improvements, though these findings remain preliminary given the limited scope and the comparison with a generic tool like GIMP. Overall, the proposed tool represents a promising step toward efficient and user-centered annotation workflows tailored for AL scenarios.

A promising direction for future development is the integration of machine learning models to support and accelerate the annotation process. Since Pixel Labeler is implemented in Python and follows a modular architecture, it is well-suited for embedding inference pipelines and interactive AI assistance. For example, pre-trained models for binarization, layout analysis, or semantic segmentation could be incorporated to generate annotation suggestions that the user can review and refine. Another potential advantage of such integration lies in enabling active labeling strategies, which could guide users toward annotating the most informative regions first. This would not only simplify the process but also help improve labeling accuracy and efficiency.

In addition, lightweight on-demand inference could enable new interaction paradigms, such as click-based region segmentation or real-time refinement. By combining manual annotation with automated support, the tool could evolve into a hybrid environment where human expertise is augmented by AI capabilities, particularly valuable in complex and degraded documents like historical music scores.

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